

A Comparative Study to Assess the Knowledge of Antenatal Women Regarding Prenatal Assessment Among Urban and Rural Community Area Amritsar, Punjab

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Abstract

Background:-Good care during pregnancy is important for the health of the mother and the development of the unborn baby. Pregnancy is a crucial time to promote healthy behaviour and parenting skills. Good prenatal assessment links the women and her family with the formal health system, increases the chance of using a skilled attendant at birth and contributes to good health through the life cycle. Inadequate care during this time breaks a critical link in the continuum of care, and effects both women and babies.**Method:** A comparative study was conducted with 60 antenatal women among urban and rural community area Amritsar,Punjab. **Results:** the study findings revealed that urban antenatal women had (66.7%) good knowledge and (33.3%) had average knowledge whereas rural antenatal women had (56.7%) Good knowledge score and (43.3%).the overall urban area mean knowledge score found to be 23.67 as compared to overall rural area mean knowledge score noticed as 19.20 . the data subjected for statistical unpaired t-test showed a highly significant difference($p<0.05$) existing between rural area and urban area over all mean knowledge score ($t=5.170^*$). Hence, the knowledge level is higher in urban areas than rural area. Non significant association of knowledge was found with age in years, place of residence, educational status of respondent, monthly income at $p<0.005$. significant association of knowledge was found with, source of information at $p<0.005$ of rural antenatal women. Non significant association of knowledge was found with age in years, place of residence, educational status of respondent, monthly income, source of information at $p<0.005$ of urban antenatal women. **Conclusion:** hence it can be concluded that urban antenatal mothers have more knowledge regarding prenatal assessment than antenatal women.

Keywords Comparison, Knowledge, Antenatal Women, Prenatal Assessment.

Introduction

(WHO)”

Good care during pregnancy is important for the health of the mother and the development of the unborn baby. Pregnancy is a crucial time to promote healthy behaviours and parenting skills. Good prenatal assessment links the woman and her family with the formal health system, increases the chance of using a skilled attendant at birth and contributes to good health through the life cycle. Inadequate care during this time breaks a critical link in the continuum of care, and effects both women and babies.

Wheaton et al(2016) believe that Pregnancy is a wonderful time of life that you will remember and cherish. It's a time of dreams and optimism, of a beautiful process of life and development. It's also the time to ensure a healthy process for both mother and child. A time of precaution and care, especially for those who are considered high risk.[1]

Forsyth et al(2016) states that To ensure a healthy and prepared experience, prenatal care begins with education and counseling. Being informed early-on can lead to a healthier pregnancy and a healthier baby. For the best prenatal care for the mother and developing baby, the Novant Health Maya Angelou Women's Health & Wellness Center at Novant Health Forsyth Medical Center recommends regular physical exams, which can include

prenatal screening tests for the baby, weight and blood measurement for the expecting mother, and monitoring of the growth and development of the baby.[2]

Dimes(2016) believe that Prenatal care is medical care you get during pregnancy. At each prenatal care visit, your health care provider checks on you and your growing baby. Schedule your first prenatal care checkup as soon as you think you know you're pregnant. Your provider can make sure you're healthy and you can find out your due date. Go to all your prenatal care checkups, even if you're feeling fine. All pregnant women get blood and urine tests and a blood pressure check at every visit. Your provider may recommend certain vaccinations or prenatal tests at your checkups. Prenatal tests make sure your baby is healthy and they include amniocentesis, chorionic villus sampling and ultrasound. Your provider also asks you about your family health history to see if certain medical conditions run in your family. Tell your provider how you're feeling and ask lots of questions so you know what's happening throughout your pregnancy.[3]

Objective of study

1. To assess the knowledge of rural antenatal women regarding prenatal assessment.
2. To assess the knowledge of urban antenatal women regarding antenatal assessment.
3. To compare the knowledge of antenatal women regarding prenatal assessment among rural and urban area.
4. To find out the association of knowledge of rural antenatal women with selected variables like Age in years, Place of living, Income, Educational Status of Respondent, Source of Income.
5. To find out the association of knowledge of urban antenatal women with selected variables like Age in years, place of living, income, educational status of respondent, source of income.
6. To prepare information booklet regarding importance of prenatal assessment.

Review of Literature

Gupta Kumar Rajiv (2015) study revealed that prenatal assessment is an effective tool to reduce both infant and maternal mortality rates. In spite of all efforts to reach and register every antenatal mother, the results are not up to desired level. Objectives: To assess the level of knowledge of pregnant women about ANC services and to find out the ANC utilization and factors affecting them. Materials and Methods: This cross-sectional study was carried out in October-November 2013 in Krishna Nagar village of Miran Sahib zone of block R.S. Pura. All the mothers (aged 15-49 years) in this village were interviewed using a predesigned, pretested, and semi-open-ended questionnaire. Results: The respondents had adequate knowledge about ANC services except for the minimum number of visits for ANC. Here, 89.6% (189) of the respondents had registered for ANC, of which 64.5% (136/211) and 9.9% (21/211) had registered in the 2nd trimester and 1st trimester, respectively. The results revealed that 79.1% of the deliveries were institutional. The age, literacy status, socioeconomic status (SES), and type of family had statistically significant associations with the utilization of ANC services.[17]

V. Yasodha(2014) conducted a study to assess the knowledge of primigravida mothers regarding antenatal care in rural and urban areas, to compare the knowledge of rural and urban primigravida mothers, to determine the association between the level of knowledge in rural and urban primigravida mothers with selected demographic variables, to develop an information guide sheet regarding antenatal care. Research design was descriptive. Setting was kadusonnaphalli PHC for rural and Narayanapuram PHC for urban area. Sample was 50 primigravida mothers in each rural and urban areas were selected by convenient sampling technique. Majority of 82% primigravida mothers had inadequate knowledge and 18% had moderately adequate knowledge in rural area. In urban area 54% had moderately knowledge and only 10% had adequate knowledge of antenatal care. There is no significant association found between knowledge of primigravida mothers with selected demographic variable.[18]

Sesedzai Peggie Matyukira (2013) a study was conducted to investigate the knowledge and utilisation of prenatal assessment services by pregnant women at a clinic in Ekurhuleni. A quantitative, descriptive correlational study was carried out on 90 eligible pregnant women. Data were collected with a self-administered questionnaire and analysed with the help of a statistician. The aim of the study was to investigate the knowledge and utilisation of prenatal assessment services by pregnant women at a clinic in Ekurhuleni. A quantitative, descriptive correlational study was carried out on 90 eligible pregnant women. Data were collected with a self-administered questionnaire and

analysed with the help of a statistician using the Epi Info version 7 computer program. The results of the study indicate that most women initiated ANC later than the recommendations by the World Health Organization (WHO). Over half of the respondents had overall good knowledge of prenatal assessment, but lacked knowledge of medication and screening tests done during pregnancy, some danger signs during pregnancy and of exclusive breastfeeding. Factors that were identified as associated with late initiation of prenatal assessment were current employment status, number of children, transport costs to clinic and number of antenatal visits.[19]

Assumption

- i. Urban antenatal women will have more knowledge regarding prenatal assessment than rural antenatal women.
- ii. Selected demographic variable may influence the antenatal women's knowledge regarding prenatal assessment

Delimitation

- i. The study was limited to the 60 antenatal women who are residing in the urban and rural area.
- ii. The study was limited to antenatal women who are willing to participate in the study

Methodology

Comparative approach with comparative research design was used to determine the knowledge of antenatal women regarding prenatal assessment (checkup), ascertain relationship with the variable and identified defecate area..The study was conducted in rural areas (Kot Khalsa, Wadali, Ghanupur) and urban areas (kashmiri gate, bibeksar road, guru ramdass colony, golden avenue,).

The purposive sampling technique was used to select the sample. Sample was antenatal women from rural and urban areas, Amritsar, Punjab. And sample size for study was 30 rural and 30 urban antenatal women. who were willing to participate and could understand English, punjabi or Hindi were selected.

Analysis

A structured questionnaire was used to assess the knowledge of antenatal women from selected rural and urban areas regarding prenatal assessment and to identify deficit areas. Tool consisted of following two parts.

Part I :socio demographic variables This part consisted of 5 items for obtaining personal information about subjects such as age in years, place of residence, educational status of respondent, family income, source of information.

Part II : Structured Questionnaire regarding prenatal assessment (checkups) This part consist of 28 items to assess the knowledge of antenatal women regarding prenatal assessment.

Result and Discussion

Table -1
Frequency and percentage distribution of sample characteristics

N=60

Sr. No.	Demographic Characteristics	Antenatal Rural Women		Antenatal Urban Women	
		Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
1.	Age in years				
a.	18-21 yrs	8	26.70%	8	26.70%
B	22-25 yrs	10	33.30%	19	63.30%
C	26-29 yrs	9	30.00%	2	6.70%
D	Above 29 yrs	3	10.00%	1	3.30%
2.	Place of residence				
A	Rural	30	100%	0	0
B	Urban	0	0	30	100%
3.	Educational Status of respondent				
A	Illiterate	9	30.00%	0	0.00%
B	Matric	16	53.30%	2	6.70%
C	Secondary	4	13.30%	20	66.70%
D	Graduate & above	1	3.30%	8	26.70%
4.	Monthly income(in rupees)				
A	<5000	0	0%	0	0%
B	5001-15000	15	50.00%	1	3.30%
C	15001-25000	15	50.00%	16	53.30%
D	above 25000/-	0		13	43.30%
5.	Source of information				
A	Relative/Friend	8	26.70%	13	43.30%
B	T.V/Radio	6	20.00%	4	13.30%
C	Newspapers/Magazine	6	20.00%	6	20.00%
D	Health Care	10	33.30%	7	23.30%

Hence, the description showed that the entire sample in rural and urban area was homogenous in characteristics, well proved with chi-square in which age in years, place of residence, educational status of respondent was non-significant at $p < 0.05$. and monthly income and source of information was significant at $p > 0.05$.

SECTION - 2

Objective - 1: To Access the knowledge of rural antenatal women regarding prenatal assessment

Table - 2

Frequency and percentage distribution of rural antenatal women according to level of knowledge regarding prenatal assessment

N = 30

Level of Knowledge	Grading Of knowledge	Frequency	Percentage

Good	22-28	13	43.3
Average	14-21	17	56.7
Below Average	0-14	0(0)	0(0)

Maximum Score = 28

Minimum Score = 0

Table 2 and figure8 depicts the frequency, percentage distribution of rural antenatal women according to knowledge score regarding prenatal assessment.. The rural antenatal women had (43.3%) Good knowledge score and (56.7%) Average score.

Hence, it can be concluded that majority of rural antenatal women had average knowledge score.

Objective – 2: To Access the knowledge of urban antenatal women regarding prenatal assessment

Table – 3

Frequency and percentage distribution of urban antenatal women according to level of knowledge regarding prenatal assessment

N = 30

Level of Knowledge	Grading Of knowledge	Frequency (n)	Percentage %
Good	22-28	20	66.7
Average	14-21	10	33.3
Below Average	0-14	0(0)	0(0)

Maximum Score = 28

Minimum Score = 0

Table 3 and figure8 depicts the frequency, percentage distribution and mean of antenatal women according knowledge score regarding prenatal assessment among rural and urban area. The antenatal women had (66.7%) Good knowledge score and (33.3%) Average score.

Hence, it can be concluded that majority of urban antenatal women had Good knowledge score.

Objective 3: To compare the knowledge of antenatal women regarding prenatal assessment among rural and urban area.

Table-4

Mean, mean percentage, standard deviation of knowledge of antenatal women (rural and urban)

N=30

Residence	n	Mean Score	SD	Unpaired T test
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Urban	30	23.67	±2.57	5.170*
Rural	30	19.20	±3.96	

Maximum Score = 28

*Significant p<0.05

Minimum Score = 0

NS= Non Significant

Table 4 and figure 9 depicts that the overall urban area mean knowledge score found to be 23.67 as compared to overall rural area mean knowledge score noticed as 19.20. The data subjected for statistical unpaired t-test showed a highly significant difference (p<0.05) existing between rural area and urban area over all mean knowledge score(t=5.170*). Hence, the knowledge level is higher in urban areas than rural areas

Objective 4: To find out the association of knowledge of rural antenatal women with selected demographic variables.

Table – 5

Association of level of knowledge of rural antenatal women regarding prenatal assessment with age

N = 30

Age in years	Good n(%)	Average n(%)	Below Average n(%)	n	df	χ^2
18-21	5 (62.5)	3(37.5)	0(0)	8	3	0.25 ^{NS}
22-25	2(20.0)	8 (80.0)	0(0)	10		
26-29	4(44.4)	5 (55.6)	0(0)	9		
Above 29 years	2(66.7)	1 (33.3)	0(0)	3		

Maximum Score = 28
Minimum Score = 0

*Significant p<0.05
NS= Non Significant

Table 5 and figure 10(a) association of level of knowledge of rural antenatal women regarding prenatal assessment with age in years, age 18-21 years majority (62.5%) had good knowledge score and remaining (37.5%) had average knowledge score. In age group 22-25 years, majority (80.0%) of antenatal women had average knowledge score and remaining (20.0%) of antenatal women had Good knowledge score. In age group 26-29 years, (55.6%) of antenatal women had average knowledge score and remaining (44.4%) had Good knowledge, in age group above 29 years majority (66.7%) had good knowledge score and remaining (33.3%) had average knowledge score i.e. $\chi^2 = 0.25$ which was statistically non significant at p<0.05.

Hence it can be concluded that there is no significant association of knowledge score among rural antenatal women with age

Table – 6
Association of level of knowledge of rural antenatal women regarding prenatal assessment with place of residence

N = 30

Place of Residence	Good n(%)	Average n(%)	Below Average n(%)	N	df	χ^2
Rural	13 (43.3)	17(56.7)	0(0)	30	1	3.300 ^{NS}
Urban	0 (0)	0 (0)	0(0)	0		

Maximum Score = 28
 Minimum Score = 0

*Significant p<0.05
 NS= Non Significant

Table 7(a) and figure 15(a) shows the association of knowledge score of rural antenatal women with place of residence. (56.7%) antenatal women of rural area had average knowledge and (43.3%) had Good knowledge level i.e. $\chi^2= 3.300$ which was statistically non significant at $p<0.05$.

Hence it can be concluded that there is no significant association of knowledge score of rural antenatal women with place of residence.

Table – 7
Association of level of knowledge of rural antenatal women regarding prenatal assessment with Educational Status

N = 30

Educational Status	Good n(%)	Average n(%)	Below Average n(%)	N	df	χ^2
Illiterate	2 (22.2)	7 (77.8)	0(0)	9	3	0.347 ^{NS}
Matric	8 (50.0)	8 (50.0)	0(0)	16		
Secondary	2 (50.0)	2 (50.0)	0(0)	4		
Graduate & above	1 (100)	0 (0)	0(0)	1		

Maximum Score = 28
 Minimum Score = 0

*Significant p<0.05
 NS= Non Significant

Table 6 figure 7 depict association of level of knowledge of rural antenatal women regarding prenatal assessment with educational status of respondent. rural Antenatal women with illiterate qualification had (77.8%) average knowledge and (22.2%) had Good knowledge. Antenatal women with matric qualification had (50.0%) average knowledge and (50.0%) Good knowledge, antenatal women with secondary qualification had (50.0%) Good knowledge and (50.0%) average knowledge , antenatal women with graduate and above qualification had (100%) Good knowledge. In order to explore the association of knowledge score of rural antenatal women with qualification, chi square was calculated i.e. $\chi^2=0.347$. which was statistically non significant at $p<0.05$.

Hence it can be concluded that there is no significant association of knowledge score of rural antenatal women with qualification.

Table – 8

Association of level of knowledge of rural antenatal women regarding prenatal assessment with monthly income (in rupees)

N = 30

Monthly income(in rupees)	Good n(%)	Average n(%)	Below Average n(%)	N	df	χ^2
>5000	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	1	0.26 ^{NS}
5001-15000	5 (33.3%)	10 (66.7)	0(0)	15		
15001-25000	8 (53.3%)	7 (46.7)	0(0)	15		
above 25000/-	0 (0)	0 (0)	0(0)	0(0)		

Maximum Score = 28
Minimum Score = 0

*Significant p<0.05
NS= Non Significant

Table 8 fig. 9 depicts association of level of knowledge of antenatal women (rural and urban) regarding prenatal assessments with monthly income (in rupees). It depicts that antenatal women with monthly income 5001-15000, (66.7%) had average knowledge followed by (33.3%) had Good knowledge. Similarly antenatal women with monthly income 15001-25000 (53.3%) had good knowledge followed by (46.7%) had average knowledge. In order to associate the level of knowledge and monthly income (in rupees) of rural antenatal women, chi square was calculated i.e. $\chi^2=0.269^{NS}$ which was statistically non-significant at $p>0.05$.

Hence it can be concluded that there is no significant association of knowledge score of rural antenatal women with monthly income(in rupees)

Table – 9

Association of level of knowledge of rural antenatal women regarding prenatal assessment with source of information

N = 30

Source of information	Good n(%)	Average n(%)	Below Average n(%)	N	df	χ^2
Relative/Friend	2 (25.0)	6 (75.0)	0(0)	8	3	0.013*
T.V/Radio	0 (0)	6 (100)	0(0)	6		
Newspapers/Magazine	5(83.3)	1 (16.7)	0(0)	6		
Health Care	6 (60.0)	4 (40.0)	0(0)	10		

Maximum Score = 28
Minimum Score = 0

*Significant p<0.05
NS= Non Significant

Table 9(a) and figure 17(a) shows the association of knowledge score among antenatal women with source of knowledge. antenatal women having Radio//T.V as source of information had (100%) average knowledge, antenatal women having family members/friends as source of information had (25.0%) good knowledge (75.0%) had average knowledge, antenatal women Newspaper/magazine as source of information had (83.3%) Good knowledge (16.7%) average knowledge, antenatal women having health care worker as source of information had (60%) good knowledge and (40%) had average knowledge. In order to explore the association of knowledge score of rural antenatal women with source of information, chi square was calculated i.e. $\chi^2= 0.013^*$ which was statistically significant at $p>0.05$.

Hence it can be concluded that there is significant association of knowledge score of rural antenatal women with source of information.

Objective 5: To find out the association of knowledge of urban antenatal women with selected demographic variables

Table – 5
Association of level of knowledge of urban antenatal women regarding prenatal assessment with age

N = 30

Age in years	Good n(%)	Average n(%)	Below Average n(%)	n	df	χ^2
18-21	6 (75.0)	2(25.0)	0(0)	8	3	0.75 ^{NS}
22-25	12(63.2)	7 (36.8)	0(0)	19		
26-29	1(50.0)	1 (50.0)	0(0)	2		
Above 29 years	1(100)	0 (0)	0(0)	1		

Maximum Score = 28
 Minimum Score = 0

*Significant p<0.05
 NS= Non Significant

Table 4(a) and figure 10(a) association of level of knowledge of urban antenatal women regarding prenatal assessment with age. in age group 18-21 years majority (75.0%) had good knowledge score and remaining (25.0%) had average knowledge score. In age group 22-25 years, majority (36.8%) of antenatal women had average knowledge score and remaining (63.2%) of antenatal women had Good knowledge score. In age group 26-29 years, (50%) of antenatal women had average knowledge score and remaining (50%) had Good knowledge, in age group above 29 years majority (100%) had good knowledge score.

Hence it can be concluded that there is no significant association of knowledge score of urban antenatal women with age

Table – 6
Association of level of knowledge of urban antenatal women regarding prenatal assessment with place of residence

N = 30

Place of Residence	Good n(%)	Average n(%)	Below Average n(%)	N	df	χ^2
Rural	0 (0)	0 (0)	0(0)	0 (0)	1	3.300 ^{NS}
Urban	20 (66.7)	10 (33.3)	0(0)	30		

Maximum Score = 28
 Minimum Score = 0

*Significant p<0.05
 NS= Non Significant

Table 7(a) and figure 15(a) shows the association of knowledge score of urban antenatal women with place of residence. (33.3%) antenatal women of urban area had average knowledge and (66.3%) had Good knowledge level i.e. $\chi^2= 3.300$ which was statistically non significant at p<0.05.

Hence it can be concluded that there is no significant association of knowledge score of urban antenatal women with place of residence.

Table – 7
Association of level of knowledge of urban antenatal women regarding prenatal assessment with Educational Status

N = 30

Educational Status	Good n(%)	Average n(%)	Below Average n(%)	N	df	χ^2
Illiterate	0 (0)	0 (0)	0(0)	0	2	0.392 ^{NS}
Matric	1 (50.0)	1 (50.0)	0(0)	2		
Secondary	15 (75.0)	5 (25.0)	0(0)	20		
Graduate & above	4 (50)	4 (50)	0(0)	8		

Maximum Score = 28
 Minimum Score = 0

*Significant p<0.05
 NS= Non Significant

Table 6 figure 7 depict association of level of knowledge of urban antenatal women regarding prenatal assessment with educational status of respondent. Urban antenatal

women with matric qualification had (50.0%) average knowledge and (50.0%) Good knowledge, antenatal women with secondary qualification had (75.0%) Good knowledge and (25.0%) average knowledge , antenatal women with graduate and above qualification had (50%) Good knowledge and (50%) had average knowledge. In order to explore the association of knowledge score of urban antenatal women with qualification, chi square was calculated i.e. $\chi^2=0.392$. which was statistically non significant at $p<0.05$.

Hence it can be concluded that there is no significant association of knowledge score of urban antenatal women with qualification.

Table – 8
Association of level of knowledge of urban antenatal women regarding prenatal assessment with monthly income (in rupees)

Monthly income(in rupees)	Good n(%)	Average n(%)	Below Average n(%)	N	df	χ^2
>5000	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	2	0.254 ^{NS}
5001-15000	0 (0%)	1 (100)	0(0)	1		
15001-25000	10 (62.5%)	6 (37.5)	0(0)	16		
above 25000/-	10 (76.9)	3 (23.1)	0(0)	13(0)		

Maximum Score = 28
Minimum Score = 0

*Significant $p<0.05$
NS= Non Significant

Table 8 fig. 9 depicts association of level of knowledge of urban antenatal women regarding prenatal assessments with monthly income (in rupees). It depicts that antenatal women with monthly income 5001-15000, (100%) had average knowledge. Similarly antenatal women with monthly income 15001-25000 (62.5%) had good knowledge followed by (37.5%) had average knowledge. Similarly antenatal women with monthly income above 25000, majority (76.9%) had good knowledge followed by (23.1%) had average knowledge. In order to associate the level of knowledge of urban antenatal women with monthly income. chi square was calculated i.e. $\chi^2=0.254^*$. which was statistically non significant at $p>0.05$.

Hence it can be concluded that there is no significant association of knowledge score of urban antenatal women with monthly income(in rupees)

Table – 9
Association of level of knowledge of urban antenatal women regarding prenatal assessment with source of information

Source of information	Good n(%)	Average n(%)	Below Average n(%)	N	Df	χ^2
Relative/Friend	8 (61.5)	5 (38.5)	0(0)	8	3	0.179 ^{NS}
T.V/Radio	2 (50)	2 (50)	0(0)	6		
Newspapers/Magazine	3 (50)	3 (50)	0(0)	6		
Health Care	7 (100)	0 (0)	0(0)	10		

Maximum Score = 28
Minimum Score = 0

*Significant $p<0.05$
NS= Non Significant

Table 9(a) and figure 17(a) shows the association of knowledge score of antenatal women with source of knowledge. antenatal women having Radio//T.V as source of information had (50%) average knowledge (50%) good knowledge, antenatal women having family members/friends as source of information had (61.5%) good knowledge (38.5%) had average knowledge, antenatal women Newspaper/magazine as source of information had (50%) Good knowledge (50%) average knowledge, antenatal women having health care worker as source of information had (100%) good knowledge. In order to explore the association of knowledge score of urban antenatal women with source of information, chi square was calculated i.e. $\chi^2= 0.179$ which was statistically non significant at $p>0.05$.

Hence it can be concluded that there is no significant association of knowledge score of urban antenatal women with source of information

Conclusion

The major goal of nursing practice is to impart knowledge and bring about changes in the people's unhealthy practices.

The present study was done to Compare and access the Knowledge regarding prenatal assessment among antenatal women at selected urban and rural area of Amritsar, Punjab on the basis of the study the following conclusions were made.

The results revealed that majority of the rural antenatal.(43.3%)have good knowledge, (56.7%) rural antenatal mothers have average knowledge and (66.7%) urban antenatal women have good knowledge, (33.3%) have average knowledge. It indicates that urban antenatal mothers have more knowledge regarding prenatal assessment than rural antenatal women.

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